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LEARNING DISABILITY IN CHILDREN: A THEORETICAL OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

The present article deals with the important factors related to learning disability such as the academic characteristics of learning disability, how learning disability can be identified in an early stage and remedial measures for learning disability. It tries to give an insight into various aspects of learning disability in children that will be of help in designing the tools and administering them properly.

INTRODUCTION

All individuals, regardless of their assets and liabilities of personality and potentiality, contribute towards national development. Exceptional children, too, cannot be excluded from this. The term '*learning disability*' is used to describe a specific group of children, adolescents and adults who have problems in learning in the academic side. In the 1960's, the difficulty that many children were having with learning attracted serious attention. An increasing number of children were found unable to cope with school work specifically with reading, writing and mathematics. These children were otherwise bright, fairly articulate in their verbal expression and did not appear to have any form of mental retardation, sensory handicap or visual

impairment. Educators and professionals began to take these learning difficulties seriously. It was Dr. Samuel Kirk, while addressing a gathering of parents, first used the 'learning disability' to describe such children (Hallahan and Cruickshank, 1973).

CAUSES OF LEARNING DISABILITIES

Through experiments in animals, scientists at the National Institute of Mental Health in the U.S.A. and other research studies are examining how genes, substance abuse, pregnancy problems, and toxins may affect the developing brain.

- **Genetic Factors:** - The fact that learning disabilities tend to run in families indicates that there may be a genetic link.
- **Problems during Pregnancy or Delivery:**-In some cases, the mother's immune system reacts to the fetus and attacks it as if it were an infection. This type of disruption seems to cause newly formed brain cells to settle in the wrong part of the brain. Or, during delivery, the umbilical cord may become twisted and temporarily cut off oxygen to the fetus. It impairs brain functions and lead to learning disability.
- **Toxins in the Child's Environment:**-Cadmium and lead, both prevalent in the environment, are becoming a leading focus of neurological research. Cadmium, get into the soil, then into the food we eat. Lead was once common in paint & petrol, and is still present in some water pipes.

ACADEMIC CHARACTERISTICS

The National Joint Committee for Learning Disabilities (NJCLD) defines learning disabilities as *disorders manifested by significant difficulties in the acquisition and use of listening, speaking, reading, writing, reasoning*

or mathematical abilities. This section will review the basic characteristics of disabilities in areas of reading, written language, mathematics and oral language.

1. Reading Disability Characteristics (Dyslexia).

Reading problems include poor comprehension, poor word-attack skills, and poor word recognition. Developing word-recognition skills is directly related to continuing knowledge base development. Many individuals with L.D will not learn to read adequately and will need alternative knowledge-acquisition methods.

2. Written Language Disability Characteristics (Dysgraphia)

Writing is also a problem area for the learning disabled with problems in both convention and composition. These difficulties are longlasting appearing throughout adulthood.

3 Oral Language Disability Characteristics

Pervasive language disabilities are a recognized characteristic of individuals with learning disability (Lenneberg, 1967, Marge, 1972). Communicative competence is a deficit area in individuals with learning disabilities. On several gross measures of communicative competence, no apparent differences emerge between individuals with L.D and without L.D (Mathinos, 1988). Subtle aspects (e.g. strategy usage) however did emerge. These subtleties relate to the quality and success of communicative interactions and affect students, teacher and other adults in educational settings (McCord & Hayness, 1988).

4. Mathematical Disability Characteristics (Dyscalculia)

The area of mathematics consists of both computational disabilities and problem-solving disabilities. Learning disabled individuals have problems in both areas. Mathematical learning disability can occur both with

and without other academic disabilities. Computational disabilities relate to manipulating arithmetic symbols and performing mathematical calculations. It is referred to as dyscalculia and calculia (partial or complete absence of mathematical ability respectively). Recent researches suggest that computational difficulties are related to ineffective or inefficient internal data manipulation and memory (Fleishmer, Gernett and Shepherd, 1980; and Houck et al., 1980). Poor symbol interpretation usually results in errors in applying basic arithmetic, which increases with problem complexity. In theory, the importance of shared cognition, contextualized reasoning and situation, specific competencies are emphasized, in contrast to the individual cognition, abstract reasoning and generalized competencies reinforced in schools (Resnick, 1987).

ATTENTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

1. Attention Deficit Characteristics

Distractibility and attention problems are often cited as characteristics of individuals with learning disability (Chalfont & Sachffin, 1969; Cruickshank & Hallahan, 1973). Some authors use Attention deficits or inattentive behaviour as a characteristic to identify individuals with L.D (Hallahan & Kauffman, 1988, and Hallahan & Reeve, 1980). Individuals with hyperactivity have a constitutional predisposition involving poor impulse control an inability to sustain attention and poorly modulated arousal levels which result in a tendency to seek stimulation and salience

2. Attention Deficit Disorder

Interest in the attention abilities of individuals in the learning disabilities was enhanced during the early 1980s, when the DSM-III classification system (American Psychiatric Association, 1980)

recommended that there should be a classification of Attention Deficit Disorder (ADD) and that ADD exists both with and without hyperactivity. The majority of investigators have accepted the concept of ADD. Present estimates suggest that approximately 33 per cent of the learning disabilities population satisfies the diagnostic criteria for ADD (Shaywitz, 1986). The 1980 DSM III classification had provisions for ADD with and without hyperactivity. Since most individuals with learning disabilities are not hyperactive, this allowed any child diagnosed as having learning difficulties and being distractible to be labeled ADD. Subsequently the new DSM-III-R (American Psychiatric Association, 1987) classification has been modified to include inattention, impulsivity and overactivity under one classification, deemed Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. (ADHD).

SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS

Even though there is considerable controversy there is even some evidence that the factors that first set these children (LD) apart from their classmates, thereby triggering the referral and diagnostic process, may be problems in social adjustments rather than academic underachievement (Pearl, Donahue & Bryan, 1986). Social problems affect individuals' feelings of acceptance, self-esteem, and perceptions of how others view him or her. They are spurned as friends, generally less popular, ignored in social situations and generally rejected (Donahue & Prescott, 1983; Garrett & Crump, 1980; and Siperstein & Goding, 1983). A significant amount of research suggests that individuals with learning disabilities have social problems with respect to their interaction. For example, in classrooms individuals with learning disabilities were often viewed as off-task and distractible (Feegans & Mckim, 1982; Gettinger & Foyne, 1982; Mckim,

McClure & Feegans, 1982). This type of behaviour has been found to elicit teacher interactions that are focused on behaviour management and behaviour correction (Siperstein & Goding, 1983). When interacting with peers, individuals with learning disabilities are found to use more derogatory comments and are unable to control and sustain conversations (Bryan et al., 1982). It is clear that individuals with learning difficulties exhibit negative social behaviours; the explanations for these behaviours are less clear. It is possible that individuals with learning disabilities are unable to adequately perceive social situations (Gerber & Zinkgraf, 1982).

IDENTIFICATION OF LEARNING DISABILITY

The parents and doctor are watching for the child to achieve developmental milestones. The pediatrician may observe more subtle signs of minor neurological damage, such as a lack of coordination. But the classroom teacher, in fact, may be the first to notice the child's persistent difficulties in reading, writing, or arithmetic. Actual diagnosis of learning disabilities is made using standardized tests but each type of LD is diagnosed in slightly different ways.

REMEDIAL MEASURES IN THE TEACHING OF LEARNING DISABLED

- All disciplines must learn to work together and share their knowledge as well as their resources, so as to direct this pool of information at the child with a problem.
- Identifying the child with a problem as quickly and as early as possible & a program of remediation should be undertaken.

- The child and his parents must be included in every step of planning with understanding and mutual cooperation between all parties involved
- It must be firmly established that there is but one person who is responsible for the ultimate learning progress of the child, and that is the teacher.

The School Responsibilities

It is urgent that the school and its component parts take an active part in the identification of the learning disabilities. The teacher must point out specific problem areas that have been observed in terms of academic performance, classroom behavior, peer relationships, child's day-to-day activities, and performance and can decide whether this meets the school's expectations for this particular child. The teacher can also be quite helpful to the doctor by providing a descriptive account of the child's behaviour with comments on why it is considered abnormal behaviour for that particular child

The Parents' Role

A most important part of our triangle is the role of the persons ultimately responsible for the child - the parents. Without the help, cooperation, advice, and understanding of the parents, there will be very little long-lasting remediation.

MODELS FOR REMEDIAL TEACHING

Some models of remedial teaching which are very helpful to the learning disabled children in overcoming their difficulties are given below:

1. Resource Room Model: The resource room employs a teacher with some background in special education. He/she works in collaboration with the classroom teachers, on an average, one teacher can generally serve eighteen

students per week and it would be self-defeating to increase the number in the resource room simply because teachers in the regular classroom cannot cope with difficult children.

2 Itinerant Programme: Another way of implementing a remedial programme is to appoint an expert teacher to come into school on specific days of the week to teach the children with learning disabilities. The itinerant teacher generally works with several schools.

3 Special Education Programmes: The special education programme involves Diagnostic Prescriptive Approach in which Ability Training Model (Process Model) and Skill Training Model (Task Analysis Model) can be employed as remedial measures. Psycholinguistic training, visual perceptual approach, perceptual motor approach, multi-sensory approach can be used by making necessary modifications as remedial measures for learning disabled children.

CONCLUSION

Learning disability is a disorder which can be remedied using appropriate instructional strategies. The early diagnosis of the problem is very important in remedial teaching as it is very difficult to correct a child in a later stage. Parents, teacher's educationists and doctors all should coordinate in finalizing the strategy required for the intervention in teaching the learning disabled child. Schools should adopt flexible approaches to testing and evaluation of the learning disabled child. There must be at least one fulltime teacher who is a trained special educator and has experience with using specific remedial methods in teaching reading, writing and mathematics. In this era of information technology, specific software can be easily developed which will be of great use to the learning disabled children

in overcoming the difficulties they face in reading, listening and mathematics. By practicing these techniques at an early stage, the learning disabled child can be mainstreamed without much difficulty.

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